

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR STUDYING
CULTURAL ISSUES IN THE LYCEUM HISTORY COURSE

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Abstract: *History education can be defined as a specially organized process of developing the ability of students to independently solve problems that have social and personal significance in various fields of activity, based on the study of the history of society. The main goal of historical education is to identify and study the basic laws of the development of society, the formation of historical thinking among students. The purpose of the article is to analyze psychological and pedagogical foundations for studying cultural issues in the lyceum history course.*

Keywords and phrases: *necessitates, practice, political development, applied art, cultural products, historical facts, rich opportunities, cultural horizons*

Currently, there is a process of changing the system of historical views, which began more than 10 years ago. Historians are gradually moving away from the formational approach to the study of history, and the civilizational approach has recently taken a leading position [1]. In this regard, the entire structure of historical knowledge is changing, more and more attention is paid to the problems of cultural development, the problems of mutual attention of culture and society, its social structure, type of government, and habitat. The emergence of new points of view, the change in attitude towards culture in the direction of increasing interest in it give rise to new approaches that are not reflected in lyceum textbooks. The emergence of new types of lyceums, the curriculum of which includes expanded blocks of information on culture, also necessitates the creation of a unified concept of teaching the development of culture in the lyceum history course.

Today, there are different approaches to the presentation of historical and cultural material in lyceums, but in practice it is usually a simple addition to the overall picture of historical development. Meanwhile, it is impossible to create a full-fledged image of the era in students without its full-fledged assimilation with an eventful history. A deep self-valuable study of cultural and historical traditions helps to comprehend the processes of social and political development at a higher level, trace economic and social changes and at the same time create prerequisites for expanding the cultural horizons of students.

The reasons for the lack of attention to cultural issues in the teaching of history lie in the position of society and the authors of textbooks [2]. Today, almost all lyceum textbooks are dominated by the traditional (since the 19th century) personalistic approach to the study of culture: the paragraphs are crammed with the names of famous cultural figures and their achievements. Of course, it is necessary to know the names and

the largest discoveries in the field of culture, but when this becomes the main way of organizing the educational process, then the assimilation of such a huge amount of material by a student in this form is simply impossible. In addition, no connection of the artist or writer with society can be traced with this approach, which does not contribute to the effective assimilation of the subject as a whole. Persons must be chosen according to the problematic principle, showing the closest connection of cultural figures with the economy and political processes in society. This approach also cannot be applied to the study of everyday culture, which today is paid much attention to both academic science and teaching.

Along with the indicated approach, other ideas are used in textbooks and teaching history. The most difficult way to study culture is a value approach based on understanding in an accessible way the philosophical basis of cultural and historical content. In works of art, words, and applied art, students identify their symbolism and mythology with the help of a teacher. This contributes to a deeper knowledge of the political, economic and mental foundations of a particular society. Semantic approaches in the study of culture must be combined with the identification of the historical context, which introduces the student into the sphere of everyday life and the lives of people of a certain time.

This method is more adequate to the modern educational process than the art history approach based on the essential analysis of works of art or cultural products, although this method can be applied in some cases, and especially in the study of world artistic culture. Within the framework of this approach, styles and directions of culture are considered in a historical context.

In the modern lyceum, the aesthetic approach to the study of culture has also firmly established itself, which is based on the formation of a set of views and feelings in students in the categories of beauty and ugliness, sublime and base, tragic and comic. Cultural and historical material contains rich opportunities for developing a sense of fantasy and the ability to perceive beauty, to overcome bad taste.

The most productive approach to the study of cultural issues in the teaching of history at lyceum is an integrated approach based on a synthetic consideration of all spheres of the functioning of society and overcoming the isolated consideration of cultural and historical material. The implementation of this approach can be carried out by "implanting" material on culture into the fabric of historical events, the socio-economic and political development of society as an integral part of it. Another possible way is to study a number of socio-political and economic phenomena through cultural and historical facts and achievements.

Thus, the problem of studying culture in lyceum history courses cannot be solved by following the personalistic approach, which is the basis of educational literature. For a productive study of historical material, it is advisable to use an integrative approach, which involves the inclusion of cultural and historical plots in the general context of studying the subject. Dialogic, personality-oriented, project and hermeneutic approaches to the study of cultural history also meet modern requirements.

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